

Report on the conceptual part of the DFG research project
Open space, politics, planning, chance. Towards a better understanding of active regional
open space policy by applying the Multiple Streams Framework

Policy-making and planning for open space in urban regions

Towards a process-based theory using the Multiple Streams Framework

Step one: An approach derived from the literature

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Preface

In view of the ongoing consumption of land in Germany and many other countries, regional and long-term initiatives are urgently needed to help protect and develop **open spaces**, especially in metropolitan areas. While there have been some positive examples of such initiatives, little research has been conducted into the question of how and why open space protection and development can succeed against often strong opposition. In particular, the political dimension of the decision-making process is poorly understood in comparison to the planning dimension. And although the term “open space policy” has been coined, related investigations have so far merely touched the surface.

Therefore, the **aim of this project** is to conduct a qualitative case study on regional open space policy-making and planning in order to explain the adoption and implementation of regional open space policies. Focusing on processes, we use the well-established Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) developed by Kingdon (1984). While emphasising that policy-making has “something of a loose, messy quality” which does not follow the “tight orderly process that a rational approach specifies”, Kingdon postulates that, to increase the likelihood that a significant policy is adopted, three largely independent process streams (problem, policy and political) need to be coupled by a capable policy entrepreneur during a window of opportunity. The study proceeds in two steps. First, an MSF-based theoretical approach for explaining policy-making and planning in the field of regional open space policy is developed. Second, the approach is empirically tested using the German cases of the Emscher Landscape Park, the Rhine-Main Regional Park and the Leipzig Green Belt.

The **present report** focuses on the theoretical part of the study in which eight propositions are formulated drawing on the two relevant strands of literature: one connected to the MSF with the other dealing with open space policy-making and planning as well as related fields. We develop the theoretical approach through interpreting the MSF and adapting it to the specifics of open space policy-making and planning in conurbations characterized by complex governance settings. Thus the report provides a fresh perspective on when open space policy-making and planning can succeed. It introduces messiness and unpredictability to the analysis of the policy field. Moreover, it already can improve the basis for strategy development of committed actors. The following keywords can be named: open space policy, regional parks, landscape, policy-making, planning, conurbations, policy process. We are grateful to Gerard Hutter, Mathias Jehling and Markus Leibenath for their helpful comments on previous versions of the report. Thanks also to Derek Henderson for proofreading the text.

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1. Introduction

Open spaces are indispensable for diverse purposes such as recreation and biodiversity promotion as well as climate mitigation and adaptation. Therefore, the protection, extension and ecological improvement of open spaces is part of many sustainability strategies at all politico-administrative levels. Open spaces are particularly important in densely populated urban regions, where they can take the form of regional parks and green belts established to halt urban sprawl and enhance multiple, regional ecosystem services. Initiatives to establish and develop such urban-regional open space networks frequently encounter considerable political challenges, including resistance from actors representing alternative forms of land use such as those related to housing, transport and business development. Furthermore, conurbations are usually characterised by a complex institutional setting in which municipalities are often in strong competition with one another. Hence, it is all the more surprising to find instances of successfully created and developed regional open space networks such as the Greater Golden Horseshoe in Canada, the Green Heart of the Dutch Randstadt or the Rhine-Main Regional Park in Germany. However, the question of what determines political decision-making on land use in this respect or more specifically, how and why such urban-regional open space initiatives can prevail over time, is still inadequately answered.

There is no doubt that public policies significantly impact land consumption as well as landscape and open space development (e.g. Hawkins 2014, Plieniger et al. 2016, Colsaet et al. 2018). Some relevant statements and studies on the workings of policy-making and corresponding planning can be found under a number of headings: urban growth, urban sprawl, growth management and smart growth (e.g. Janssen-Jansen 2005, Couch et al. 2007, Pallagst 2007, Grant 2018, Siedentop et al. 2022), landscape planning and governance (Pollock-Ellwand 2001, Tress et al. 2004, Görg 2007, Leibenath & Lintz 2017, Boulton & Dedekorkut-Howes 2024), biodiversity protection (Wilkinson et al. 2013, Cash 2016, Reber et al. 2022, Mehring et al. 2024) as well as open space policy and planning (Koomen et al. 2008, van der Valk & van Dijk 2009, Wetteman-Wülk 2015, Eichhorn et al. 2024, Scott & Kirby 2024).

In-depth analyses of the functioning of political decision-making in these fields highlight the role of institutional framework conditions (van Rij 2008, Smith 2009, Kronenberg 2015). Some scholars, partly within the intellectual tradition of political economy and political ecology, have focused on conflicting interests and power (Downs 2005, Molotch 1976, Genoud 2018 or Calderon & Butler 2020). Hersperger et al. 2018) highlight territorial governance and external conditions as two factors in the making and implementation of land-use plans. More specifically, a number of publications have looked at the creation and development of open space networks such as regional parks or green belts (Amati 2008, Elmarsdóttir 2016, Keil & MacDonald 2016, Rottle 2016, Cruickshank 2018, Gailing 2018, Sturzaker & Mell 2018, Burton 2019, MacDonald et al. 2021b, Kirby et al. 2025). Some of these have focused on conurbations or metropolitan regions (Tress et al. 2004, van der Valk & van Dijk 2009, Momm-Schult et al. 2013).

While these studies have examined a range of sub-aspects related to our research question under different conceptual approaches and at varying analytical depth, it is true that process

theories from political science have hitherto been little used or conceptualised for this topic (one notable exception being Hersperger et al. 2014). In particular, theoretical and empirical research on open space policy has so far paid insufficient attention to the 'messiness' which exists to a certain degree in policy-making and planning in practice.

This gap can be usefully filled by Kingdon's Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) (Kingdon 1984). As Lintz (2022) showed, the MSF corresponds very well with a comprehensive empirical description of the development of the Rhine-Main Regional Park, Germany, by the regional planner and managing director Lorenz Rautenstrauch (2015a). In his report, Rautenstrauch details the twists and turns that key players had to face – or indeed were able to exploit – over a period of 25 years in establishing and developing this urban-regional open space network. It is precisely this 'messiness' and a significant degree of unpredictability in policy-making and planning processes that lies at the heart of the MSF. To date, only a few studies have explicitly adopted selected elements of the MSF to analyse policy and planning processes in the area of landscape and open space development. Two examples are van der Stoep et al. (2017), who investigated how policy attention could be mobilised for landscape values, and Gerlak et al. (2021), who examined the role of policy entrepreneurs in green infrastructure policy-making.

Originally developed as an approach within political science for agenda setting in US federal health and transport policy, the MSF has since been widely applied, although not yet systematically for open space policy. The core of the framework is the idea that three relatively independent processes or streams play a central role in policy change. Accordingly, significant political decisions occur when the problem, policy and political streams are simultaneously conducive to change and are brought or 'coupled' together by a policy entrepreneur exploiting a window of opportunity. The MSF also encompasses a number of other recognised factors and can be combined with many other approaches.

Against this backdrop and as a first step in theory development, the objective of this conceptual paper is to draw on existing literature to elaborate an MSF-based theoretical approach that explains the adoption and implementation of urban-regional open space policies focusing on policy-making and planning processes. In this context, we understand policy as the content-related outcome of those processes which are to be implemented. To realise our objective, we must interpret and adapt the original MSF to this policy field, in particular going beyond the agenda setting stage to cover the long-term development of regional open space networks. To this end, we analyse and synthesise two broad strands of literature, one connected to the MSF with the other dealing with open space policy-making and planning as well as related fields. The theoretical approach focuses on conurbations characterised by complex governance settings.

In the following, we describe the methodology used to elaborate the MSF-based theoretical approach (Section 2) before outlining the specifics of urban-regional open space policy (Section 3). Next, we highlight the main features of the MSF and briefly address its development to date (Section 4). In Section 5, which is the heart of the paper, we develop our theoretical approach by adapting the MSF to regional open space policy. To finish we reflect on the approach by considering its advantages and limitations (Section 6) before drawing some conclusions (Section 7).

2. Methodology – connecting two literature strands

In order to use the MSF to develop a theoretical approach to explain the adoption and implementation of urban-regional open space policy, two broad strands of literature were analysed and brought together iteratively. As mentioned, very few previous publications have drawn on both strands, and thus no reliable bridge has been established thus far. Firstly, the paper draws on literature dealing with and applying the MSF. Given the vast number of MSF-related studies, we focused on Kingdon (1984) and those publications generally describing the framework and its recent refinements and extensions. To these we added some more specialised articles on the refinements and extensions, particularly studies going beyond the original MSF to include further stages in the policy cycle such as decision-making and implementation. We also considered many MSF-based studies with a connection to regional open space policy such as those addressing the subnational, regional and local level, as well as those directed at environmental policy. However, due to their specificity, these studies turned out to be less helpful than expected. Secondly, the study analyses literature pertaining to the wider field of open space, landscape and spatial policy as well as planning. In particular, we looked at publications on regional parks and green belts. Some of these publications already contain very useful empirical data, particularly the comprehensive practitioner report mentioned above (Rautenstrauch 2015a). In line with the approach to theorising advocated by Swedberg (2012), this data was intensively mined to develop the specific theoretical approach to the policy field of interest here.

The question of how the five structural elements of the MSF, i.e. the three streams, the policy entrepreneur and the policy window, could be interpreted in relation to open space policy served as a guide to link the two strands. Moreover, we considered which recent refinements and extensions of the original MSF must be included into the adapted theoretical approach in order to sufficiently grasp the reality of the investigated policy field. Again, inspired by Swedberg (2012), we went systematically and intuitively back and forth between the MSF, on the one hand, and the features of open space policy-making and planning, on the other, in order to generate a synoptic comparison as an intermediary step. Identified gaps could be filled through the creative use of metaphors, analogies and categorisations (including matrices). In the following sections of the paper, therefore, the relevant aspects of the MSF and the regional open space policy are well substantiated by references from the literature.

3. Urban-regional open space: policy-making and planning

This section presents our understanding of the subject under investigation as derived from the relevant literature. The first subsection (3.1) offers basic definitions while in the second (3.2) we go into more detail regarding the dimensions and design options in the policy field.

3.1 Basic definitions

Processes in policy-making lie at the heart of this study. These are shaped by the specific characteristics of the considered policy field (Heinelt 2007). Not unexpectedly, there is no generally accepted definition of open space policy. Here we base our understanding, firstly, on the idea that policy-making is fundamentally about solving problems (Howlett 2011, 18) and, secondly,

on the fact that it can refer to particular substantive areas (May et al. 2006, 382). Accordingly, this study defines open space policy as a public activity geared towards establishing generally binding rules and decisions regarding goals, strategies, concepts, instruments, measures, projects and plans which aim at the provision of open space. Policy-making involves planning, which in this context (and in line with Kingdon 1984, 122) is defined as the preparation of these policies by experts to support – and thereby influence – political decisions. Policies and planning become regional, i.e. spanning at least two municipalities, when formulated by regional actors and/or formulated for a region (cf. May et al. 2006, 383).

Due to the restricted areal competences of subnational administrative units, these policies generally aim to achieve concrete spatial structures as detailed, for instance, in spatial sketches and plans. In this sense, strategies and concepts for the creation and the development of regional open space networks such as multifunctional regional parks, green belts, green wedges and greenways are at the core of urban-regional open space policies. In our understanding, the networks are typically established in conurbations characterised by high settlement density and a scarcity of open spaces. In addition, and importantly for this study, these have become more and more flexible, informal and embedded in complex governance settings (Tress et al. 2004, Gailing 2018). In this regard, Macdonald et al. (2021b, 804) speak of a “new generation of greenbelts” while Sturzaker & Mell (2018, 8) highlight the “[p]oliticisation of the landscape” as a relevant backdrop.

3.2 Dimensions and design options

Over decades, strategies of urban-regional open space policy have become ever more diverse, increasing the challenge of decision-making due to the now many design options in several design dimensions. These vary considerably depending on regional, state and national framework conditions and the specific functions the open spaces are expected to fulfil. The design options refer to the following four dimensions: the desired physical-spatial structures, the relation to private property owners, the way in which policy-making and planning is organised, and the use of a process-oriented strategic policy-making and planning approach.

Regarding the first dimension, the general material or physical aim of urban-regional open space policies is to provide multifunctional networks of open spaces, particularly for the purposes of leisure and recreation, climate mitigation and adaptation as well as biodiversity protection. This is realised by identifying and implementing appropriate ecological spatial structures, which can be variously shaped as, e.g. centred areas, belts or wedges. These structures reflect the locations, sizes, qualities and connections of open spaces, also taking into account the relation to adjacent land usage (e.g. Maruani & Amit-Cohen 2007, Ndubisi 2008, Quintas 2015). The desired structures can be achieved by protecting pre-existing open spaces, ecologically enhancing such spaces and/or recovering open spaces through nature restoration (Amati & Taylor 2010).

At the same time, the population’s access to and experience of nature and landscape should be ensured through hiking and biking trails, viewing towers, etc. Cultural heritage sites or sculptural artworks are often integrated into the open space network (Gailing 2007). As a soft location factor, multifunctional open spaces are also expected to enhance regional economic competitiveness (Ganser 2001, Servillo 2011). Frequently, however, there are significant complex

trade-offs and conflicts which need to be balanced, such as between economic and environmental interests, but also between outdoor recreation and biodiversity protection (as seen in Rautenstrauch 2015a, 26). In the standard case, desired land-use structures are defined by a spatial plan to varying degrees of concreteness. Similar to general spatial policy, open space policy in conurbations has to retain a flexible, long-term vision of spatial structures, which can only be implemented gradually – frequently over decades (as e.g. seen in Rautenstrauch 2015a, cf. Schwarze-Rodrian 2016). This can be attributed to the often large size of the concerned areas, the considerable costs (and a low willingness to spend money for this purpose) and the lengthy periods required for natural habitats to develop.

With regard to the second dimension of design options, namely the relation to private property owners, we must note that in many countries land is predominately in private ownership and land sales are governed by market forces (e.g. Nuisl & Couch 2007). Here there are several typical instruments which can be employed to secure space for the provision of ecosystem services within the desired spatial structures. Land that is already publicly owned can, of course, be used to establish an open space network. Municipalities can also involve private land-owners through public-private partnerships or buy land from private owners; further, regular financial grants can be offered to ensure that certain areas on private land are used in the desired way. Finally, regulations in the form of zoning plans can steer land usage on private land without compensation. Generally, however, most of the measures or projects to physically improve the ecological qualities of land, whether private or public, require public funding.

The third dimension of design options, which relates to the organisation of open space policy-making and planning, needs particular elaboration. Clearly, the formulation of material aims and targets as well as the employment of the above-mentioned instruments need to be guided in a legitimised way. To this end, specific institutional arrangements or organisational models of political decision-making (as well as the preparatory processes for these decisions) must be established to enable the provision of appropriate open spaces (see, e.g., Lintz 2016, Gailing 2018, Sturzaker & Mell 2018, Macdonald et al. 2021a, b). Four points need to be considered here. Point one refers to a general characteristic of environmental policy, namely that the development of an urban-regional open space network, for instance, is generally a demanding task that *cuts across sectors* and which must be coordinated with other policies related to, for example, housing, transport and business development, all of which are in close competition for land (Freestone 2002, Elmarsdóttir 2016, Macdonald et al. 2021a, b). From the perspective of general *spatial* policy and planning, the demands of these sectoral policies, including open space or landscape planning, should be considered when developing the overall spatial structures.

Point two deals with the specific institutional framework conditions, often referred to as the regional governance setting, that usually exists at regional level (Teles 2023). Here the need to involve a wide range of relevant actors poses a coordination challenge to the organisational model. With regard to open space policy, van der Valk & van Dijk (2009, 5) describe the regional level as a “fragmented and complex web of owners and governments”. The range of involved administrative authorities may include diverse municipalities (cities, counties, towns), specific regional organisations as well as involved state governments. Moreover, interest groups, citizens, scholars and the media can all be viewed as actors (see also Lintz 2016). While these

regional governance structures generally tend to hamper joint regional policy-making, urban-regional open space policy is perceived, at least in comparison to regional economic policy, as relatively easy to handle at regional level (Ziafati Bafarasat 2016, 257, Smith 2009, 18). As regional parks, for example, are deemed to improve the common regional identity, they are even understood as starting points for a more general regional cooperation (Gailing 2007, Rautenstrauch 2015a, 12).

Point three refers to the consideration that in some countries, such as Austria, Germany and the Netherlands, spatial planning is regulated by a complex statutory or *formal* system that stipulates detailed material goals and provisions for decision-making processes aimed at developing and implementing desired spatial structures (Macdonald et al. 2021b). In such cases, informal open space approaches can be designed to supplement the system. Where there is no (or only a rudimentary) system of formal spatial planning, however, such informal approaches can be the main strategy to ecological spatial planning in conurbations. The fourth point is to note that the financial dimension of developing regional open space networks, such as the costs of projects and planning staff, is a key aspect of the organisational model. Of particular importance here are rules that determine which municipalities must pay (and how much) and which will benefit from implemented measures. Moreover, as finances have their own additional institutional context, i.e. the budgeting processes at the municipal, regional and state level, it is vital to smartly coordinate decision-making on spatial structures and public funding.

The last design dimension of regional open space policies is of specific importance because it mainly refers to desired processes and interactions of actors within given institutional arrangements. It can be analysed particularly well with the process-oriented MSF. In line with the *zeitgeist* of communicative, collaborative and strategic planning in planning theory (e.g. Healey 1996, Albrechts 2001), a kind of informal or 'soft' strategic approach has emerged as a general guiding principle for spatial policy-making and planning. The approach recognises political and process-related dimensions of planning and can be applied by regions to varying degrees. Here we can point to the influential International Building Exhibition Emscher Park (Shaw 2002), which took place from 1989 to 1999 in Germany's old industrial Ruhr area. Following the idea of "perspective incrementalism" (Ganser et al. 1993), the exhibition strongly promoted the Emscher Landscape Park to counter the appalling environmental situation at the time. Partly drawing on the event and its concept, Selle (1994) formulated a prototypical strategic approach for a new regional open space policy that aims to overcome existing steering problems in environmental and spatial policy-making. In particular, the strategy should ensure the long-term mobilisation of political forces, media, public and funding. To this end, the key elements of the strategy are to:

- acknowledge and communicate the value of green open space;
- use the power of persuasion and strengthen public outreach;
- anchor the concept of regional open space in the hearts and minds of local people by creating images of that which is to be protected and developed;
- involve all relevant stakeholders, including businesses, and promote joint learning and cooperation;

- foster projects and enhance the creativity of experts as well as organise conducive structures and processes (Selle 1994, translated by authors).

Similar key elements can be found in various publications such as Sinning 2003, Nuisl & Couch 2007, Amati 2008, van der Valk et al. 2009, O’Sullivan et al. 2014, Ziafati Bafasarat 2016, Gailing 2018, Sturzaker & Mell 2018 and Macdonald et al. 2021a, b. We will come back to these aspects in Section 5.

4. The Multiple Streams Framework

The MSF is a well-established approach to public policy analysis, a sub-field of policy science that focuses on the analysis of policies and policy-making in specific policy fields (Blum & Schubert 2011, 10, 15). Specifically, the MSF helps elucidate significant policy change by analysing the policy process. Following Ostrom’s general definition of a framework (2005, 28), we understand the MSF as providing a general set of variables, which need to be specified and concretised in a more specific theory. The MSF was originally developed by John W. Kingdon (1984) to investigate agenda setting in US-American national health and transportation policy-making. Kingdon challenges the model of comprehensive, rational policy-making by pointing out that this activity has “something of a loose, messy quality” and does not follow the “tight orderly process that a rational approach specifies” (1984, 83). At the same time, he does not claim that policy-making is essentially random. In this section, we first focus on Kingdon’s original approach (Subsection 4.1) before touching upon recent developments (Subsection 4.2).

4.1 Main features of the original approach

Drawing heavily on the Garbage Can Model of organisational decision-making theory (Cohen et al. 1972), Kingdon makes several assumptions (Herweg et al. 2018): Ambiguity means that there can be many different understandings of problems and solutions; time constraints limit the information which can be processed; preferences are not clear, nor are competences and responsibilities; fluid participation means that the set of actors can change in the process; finally, there exist process dynamics or streams which develop independently. In his framework, Kingdon postulates the interaction of five structural elements to explain why, in agenda setting, some issues receive more attention from policy-makers than others, (Kingdon 1984, Herweg et al. 2018, Zahariadis et al. 2023). Ultimately, he hypothesises that a given issue is most likely to make it onto the political agenda when each of the five elements is in a favourable state for significant policy change (see Fig. 1).

The aspect of messiness and randomness is prominently (though not exclusively) represented in the three identified streams, namely the problem, policy and political streams, which flow through the political system. They are assumed to be “largely independent of one another”, following their “own dynamics and rules” (Kingdon 1984, 20). For this reason, and in a strict sense, it is only by chance that all three streams will be in a favourable state at the same time. The problem stream consists of problems, i.e. conditions that deviate from ideal situations and are interpreted as deplorable or improvable. A wide range of problems compete for public attention. Awareness of these problems amongst politicians and their sense of urgency are

driven by studies and indicators, by focusing events or by feedback from the outcome of previous policies. While the problem stream can be quite volatile, the policies in the policy stream develop rather steadily. Experts in policy communities elaborate policy options that have the potential to resolve problems. Criteria for the expected success of policies are technical feasibility, financial viability and value acceptability. The political stream represents the general propensity of politicians to deal with a certain problem in a certain way. This underlines the importance of the particular individual in charge of decision-making at a specific juncture, assuming that personnel turnover is high and changing coalitions occur frequently. Moreover, politicians take into account the viewpoints and activities of organised interest groups and the potentially volatile mood of the population. Although all potential actors can contribute to any and all streams, there do exist certain affinities, such as the work done by experts predominately in the policy stream (Kingdon 1984, 20, 206).

Simultaneous favourability or “ripeness” of the streams is a necessary but insufficient condition for success. A capable policy entrepreneur must become active in order to “couple” the streams. Policy entrepreneurs strive to convince receptive policy-makers to employ a particular policy to solve specific problems. They may even seek out topical problems to justify a certain policy (Kingdon 1984, 129). In our interpretation, the streams become coupled in the sense that specific problems from the vast problem stream and specific policies from the vast policy stream are brought together with the political stream. The entrepreneur quickly intensifies their push towards coupling when they perceive an opportune moment, i.e. a favourable temporary opportunity, called the policy window. These windows can arise through changes in the problem or political stream, such as following a natural disaster or a change in government or through scheduled decision opportunities, such as when a programme is up for renewal. If the entrepreneur is successful, the agenda is set. As Kingdon (1984, 21) puts it: “Solutions become joined to problems, and both of them are joined to favourable political forces.” Although the MSF basically opposes the comprehensive, rational model of policy-making, the final political decision on policies obviously needs to be *perceived* as convincing and rational.

Fig. 1: How the Multiple Streams Framework explains policy-making processes. Source: Illustration based on the work of Kingdon (1984), Rüb (2014) and Lintz (2022)

4.2 Further developments of the approach

As already documented by Jones et al. in 2016, Kingdon's seminal work on the MSF stimulated literally hundreds of later studies, which either took up the framework or focused on individual variables within it. These studies range across diverse policy fields in different countries and at various politico-administrative levels. In part as a reaction to criticism, the original approach has been further developed through a number of refinements and extensions, documented in several key publications of recent years, e.g. Herweg et al. (2018), Ritter & Lancaster (2018) and Zahariadis et al. (2023).

Some refinements have been proposed, for instance, regarding the problem stream. Specifically, Knaggård (2015) introduced a problem broker, while Mukherjee and Howlett (2015) added epistemic communities as a key group of actors. With regard to the policy stream, Herweg et al. (2018) improved our understanding of policy communities and Simons and Voß (2018) introduced the concept of instrument constituencies and the transfer of policy ideas. Regarding the political stream, Howlett et al. (2017) suggested that the Advocacy Coalition Framework should be incorporated into the MSF. Other scholars have elaborated on the general role of actors (Mukherjee & Howlett 2015), networks (Reardon 2018) and institutions (Bolkvasi & Yildirim 2022). In addition, there have been refinements to the notions of entrepreneurship and coupling: Herweg et al. (2015) introduced collective entrepreneurship and the role of a political entrepreneur; Cairney (2018) discussed entrepreneurial strategies and specific venues or arenas that entrepreneurs can use; Dolan & Blum (2023) and Dolan (2021) introduced ideas of partial coupling and issue linking. Finally, Töller (2023) showed that the MSF can also be used to explain non-decisions or negative decisions.

Unfortunately, it has proved impossible to entirely eliminate the (partial) lack of clarity and consistency in Kingdon's work, particularly stemming from the use of the stream metaphor. This means that there is still a lot of room and need for interpretation. Balancing parsimony and complexity (cf. Howlett et al. 2015), we will explore some of the refinements which we deem – in this first step of theory development – most relevant for an MSF-based theoretical approach to the field of urban-regional open space policy. The main extension is to move beyond agenda setting.

5. An MSF-based theoretical approach

As mentioned, the objective of this conceptual paper is to draw on existing literature to elaborate an MSF-based theoretical approach that explains the adoption and implementation of urban-regional open space policies focusing on policy-making and planning processes. To do so, we interpret and adapt the MSF to this policy field in line with the recommendations of Zohlnhöfer et al. (2022). From the synthesis of the relevant literature strands we derive a set of eight qualitative propositions which summarise the approach. In the following, we start with the overarching adaptations which are relevant to more than one of the five elements of the MSF (Section 5.1). Then the interpretation and adaptation of each of the five MSF elements is discussed (Section 5.2).

In anticipation of these two sections and taking into account the aim of going beyond agenda setting and distinguishing between an initial and an implementation phase, we can here already formulate the first proposition to characterise the general theoretical approach which will later be qualified by additional propositions:

P1 – General approach: *The adoption of a significant positive change in urban-regional open space policy in the initial phase is most likely if the problem, policy and political streams are in a favourable state, and a policy entrepreneur exploits a policy window to couple the streams. Successful implementation is most likely if the three streams continue to be favourable and a policy entrepreneur keeps them coupled.*

5.1 Overarching adaptations

The overarching adaptations of the MSF to urban-regional open space policy allow to go beyond agenda setting (Part 5.1.1), but also to better reflect the complex institutional setting (Part 5.1.2). These two aspects are summarised in the second proposition.

5.1.1 Beyond agenda setting

As the analysis of urban-regional open space policy in Section 3 showed, it is necessary to investigate land use decision-making over long periods of time in order to capture and understand real physical changes on the ground; the mere consideration of agenda setting is here simply insufficient. To this end, we expand on Kingdon's approach to also consider the policy formation and decision-making stage, thereby completing what we call the initial phase. In addition, the often long-term implementation phase needs to be taken into account as implementation is of particular importance in urban-regional open space strategies (Gailing 2018, 6). Although there are considerable theoretical challenges when one attempts to go beyond agenda setting, several recent publications have shown that the MSF and its core features can be extended conceptually in this way, e.g. Herweg et al. (2015) on decision-making as well as Zahariadis and Exadaktylos (2016) and Fowler (2022) on implementation. In a series of publications, Howlett and colleagues have even envisaged developing an MSF-based general framework of the policy process that encompasses the stages of the policy cycle up to the implementation stage (Howlett et al. 2015, Howlett 2019, Goyal & Howlett 2020). However, these developments are still in their infancy and there is no consensus on what such an approach might look like in detail. One key insight is that, in the initial phase, entrepreneurship strives to couple the three streams so as to secure the adoption of a policy. Then, once the policy has been adopted, entrepreneurial attention turns to stabilising the change by keeping the streams coupled as well as to facilitating proper implementation and further development of the urban-regional open space strategy. Thus, the five elements of the MSF need to remain favourable throughout the whole policy cycle and policy entrepreneurship needs to be ensured all along.

Generally speaking, two important repercussions of going beyond Kingdon's agenda setting stage are, firstly, that the institutional framework assumes a much bigger role than in the original MSF and, secondly, processes become more structured (Herweg et al. 2018). According to the Policy Cycle-Actor Hourglass model, the number of actors involved may decrease from the agenda setting stage to the decision-making stage before increasing again in the implementation stage (Howlett et al. 2020, 12). The set of involved persons can also change over time.

While the policy cycle and the two-phases model help structure complex processes, it is necessary to note that – in contrast to the early concept of policy stages and reflecting Kingdon’s criticism (1984, 83) – this does not imply that policy-making is generally conducted in a systematic or linear fashion. Rather it is the case that many relevant interdependent processes such as policy formulation and implementation run simultaneously or overlap in varying time frames (cf. Gailing 2018, 6, cf. also to Howlett et al. 2020, 12).

It can be challenging to apply the concept of the initial and the implementation phase to very long periods of time. At least two interpretations seem possible, referring to different temporal scales and allowing for a more differentiated analysis. First, the overall evolution of an urban-regional open space network can be conceptualised as a sequence consisting of the two phases. To determine the end of the first phase and the beginning of the second, we have to select a policy decision viewed as the most fundamental to the urban-regional open space strategy. This could be the adoption of a ‘fully-fledged’ open space concept after a major multi-step conceptualisation phase. The agenda setting, policy formulation and decision-making stages can then be defined as the phase leading to the policy adoption. Accordingly, the longer-term implementation stage can be defined as the phase following the policy adoption. Second, one can imagine that significant policy decisions are taken within this long-term implementation phase yet at a much shorter time scale, again embedded in a sequence of a (specific) initial phase and a (specific) implementation phase. Such a decision may be needed when one or more streams become less favourable and actually decouple. The corresponding challenge for entrepreneurship will be discussed in Part 5.2.6. On the other hand, we can also imagine a sequence of a (specific) initial phase and a (specific) implementation phase when new major open space projects are suggested which were not envisaged when the concept was first established.

5.1.2 Specific institutional complexity

To take account of the mentioned complex setting of urban-regional open space policy (Subsection 3.2.), at least two more basic adaptations are needed. The first is related to the fact that, in contrast to Kingdon’s US example, relevant political decisions in our case are taken within regional governance, i.e. within a multi-level, multi-sector and multi-actor setting. This implies that the approval and implementation of an urban-regional open space strategy will be realised through multiple, sequential, interdependent and nested decisions at various levels or venues. For example, there may be an interplay of intra-municipal and inter-municipal decisions (Lintz 2016). Moreover, the streams may flow across political levels (Knaggård & Hildingsson 2023). Second, as indicated above, we must remember that in the specific field of urban-regional open space policy, there are often two differently institutionalised processes of political decision-making for open spaces, which do not necessarily proceed at the same time. These are, on the one hand, the allocation of land uses to spaces (spatial planning) and, on the other, the allocation of financial resources to land uses (budgeting). Thus, we see that the creation and implementation of an urban-regional open space strategy is shaped by complex web of various kinds of nested decisions (cf. Möck et al. 2022, Fowler 2023, 23). Now we are in a position to formulate our second proposition regarding the overarching adaptations:

P2 – Overarching adaptations: To explain long-term physical development of open space networks, the analysis of urban-regional open space strategies has to go beyond agenda setting. At least two types of sequences, each consisting of an initial and an implementation phase,

can be distinguished: (1) a sequence spanning the overall evolution of the open space network; and (2) the short-term sequences nested within the long-term implementation phase. Taking into account the regional governance setting and the distinction between spatial and financial planning, the development of urban-regional open space strategies is shaped by complex web of nested decisions.

5.2 Adaptation of the MSF elements

In this subsection, we interpret and adapt each of the five key elements of the MSF according to the main features of urban-regional open space policy-making and planning (see Fig. 1). These elements will be further developed in the following six parts by incorporating those refinements and extensions from recent MSF-scholarship that we consider relevant and helpful. Starting with the three streams, we will specifically elaborate their subcomponents, which are the drivers that influence the stream dynamics (Parts 5.2.1. to 5.2.3). This general understanding of the stream dynamics is fundamental to the remaining parts. There we will take a detailed look at the other MSF elements also in regard to the implications of extending the MSF beyond the agenda setting stage by dividing the policy process into an initial and an implementation phase. We will begin by analysing the central figure of the policy entrepreneur and the coupling activities (Part 5.2.4) before examining the implications for the conceptualisation of the window of opportunity (Part 5.2.5). Then, in Part 5.2.6, we return to the notion of the three streams, exploring how entrepreneurship and stream dynamics interact during the implementation phase. The focus here is on disentangling the risks of potential decoupling processes. Each individual part of the subsection ends with a summary, formulated as a proposition for the MSF element and its role in the field of urban-regional open space policy.

5.2.1 Problem stream

As stated in Section 4, problems arise from a specific interpretation of one or more issues that constitute conditions deviant from an ideal situation. In other words, any condition can be presented or framed in a way that turns it into a problem (Kingdon 1984, 115f., Herweg et al. 2018, 22). Accordingly, the literature on urban-regional open space policy offers a wide range of issues considered to be problems which potentially justify the protection and enhancement of the remaining open spaces. Typical examples are urban sprawl, expanding economic and industrial infrastructure, climate change, biodiversity loss and ecological damage, as well as a lack of recreational areas and unsatisfactory living conditions for residents and skilled workforce (Caspersen et al. 2006, Gailing 2007, Keil & Macdonald 2016, Zepp 2018). As can be seen from this non-exhaustive list, social, economic and ecological aspects are linked together in the process of constructing and defining a problem, with urban-regional landscapes serving as a common, spatial reference point (Bradely 2019). Moreover, these processes are also embedded in similar discussions taking place in other regions as well as at national, European and international level (Buxton & Goodman 2004, Amati 2008, Siedentop et al. 2016).

In the original MSF, the main drivers of the problem stream are studies and indicators, focusing events and policy feedback (see Subsection 4.1). Yet in contrast to Kingdon's conception of problem construction (1984, p. 90ff), the role of studies and indicators as drivers bringing these multiple issues to the attention of politicians seems to be supportive rather than decisive in this policy field. This may be due to the fact that, particularly in the case of slowly increasing

land consumption, palpable consequences based on scientific research are difficult to capture and do not raise immediate awareness (Lintzmeyer et al. 2021). Moreover, unlike in the MSF literature, where focusing events in the form of sudden, unpredictable incidents are often highlighted as drivers of the problem stream (Birkland & Warnement 2013), the literature on urban-regional open space policies and spatial planning contains very few indications of such single, high-impact events. Instead it is the notion of slow-burning crises or issues (Lintzmeyer et al. 2021), such as a legacy of contaminated sites and devastated landscapes in deindustrialised areas or continued urban sprawl in prospering areas, that seems to create sufficient pressure on politicians to act.

Consequently, we assume that two more variants of focusing events mentioned by Kingdon could more vigorously raise awareness of a problem and thus need to be considered as important specifications: personal experience (Kingdon 1984, 102) and the presence of a strong symbol (ibid, 97 f., see also Taylor et al. 2023). The former refers to the fact that experts and policy-makers residing in a region are likely to have their own lived experiences of the social, economic and ecological challenges discussed in that space. In this way, they are more open to perceiving these issues as urgent problems to be solved by public policies. In the literature on urban-regional open space policies for regional park or green belt strategies, we find evidence that this link is addressed by the concepts of place-making (Fürst et al. 2005, Krause 2014) and territorial or regional identity (Paasi 2003, Bradely 2019). Symbols, the third variant of focusing events, can reinforce or focus the attention of policy-makers by capturing “in a nutshell some sort of reality that people already sense in a vaguer, more diffuse way” (Kingdon 1984, 103). In our case, degraded landscapes can be interpreted as such a symbol. The poor aesthetical value of fragmented urban-regional open spaces (Röhring & Gailing 2005, 8) is part of the perceived everyday reality of the population and the policy-makers. It stands symbolically for the poor quality of life due to urban sprawl (Rautenstrauch 2015b, 8). The image of degraded landscapes and in particular its positively connotated counterpart, the vision of scenic landscapes, thus becomes relevant once again in the policy stream (Part 5.2.2).

The third driver of the problem stream is policy feedback, which occurs as a reaction to the negative outcomes of adopted instruments and strategies (Kingdon 1984, 100 ff.). In the literature on regional open space planning, for example, urban sprawl and landscape degradation are partly attributed to the incapacity of formal planning to prevent further soil sealing, thus leading to the excessive designation of land for economic or infrastructure development (Gailing 2018, 3, Selle 1994). Seen through the MSF lens, this can be understood as policy feedback to these formal planning regulations and their negative impacts on open spaces (Amati & Taylor 2010, Dettmar 2014). We can sum up the considerations of this part in our next proposition:

P3 – Problem stream: In this stream, problem construction related to open spaces occurs when socio-economic and ecological issues are linked to urban-regional landscapes. Key drivers of the problem stream are personal, place-specific everyday experiences, and the use of “degraded landscapes” as a symbol for a deficient provision of open space. Negative policy feedback on planning instruments is an additional driver of the problem stream.

5.2.2 Policy stream

As just discussed, urban-regional open space strategies such as regional parks emerge in policy communities as potential solutions to a variety of problems. With regard to the need for the coordination of sectoral policies (Subsection 3.2; Kidd 2013, Siedentop et al. 2022) it is important that such communities integrate experts from different policy fields or disciplines. The specific design options (cf. Section 3.2) are the result of long-term, constant processes of evolution and recombination, which Kingdon refers to as "softening up" (Kingdon 1984, 134ff.). Based on the spatial extension to Kingdon's original conception devised by Simons and Voß (2018), we distinguish, on the one hand, between general blueprints (ibid. p. 19) or policy models, and their regional adaptations, on the other. These are discussed and developed within a regional community of experts. In the field of urban-regional open space policy-making and planning, we highlight the above-mentioned International Building Exhibition Emscher Park with its support for the Emscher Landscape Park as an example of a widely acknowledged general blueprint (Pinch & Adams 2013). This exhibition introduced a new model for planning policies, one that combines project-, collaboration- and communication-based approaches. In doing so, it stimulated the creation of many urban-regional open space initiatives in Germany that can be understood as specific regional adaptations.

The successful regional adaptation of these open space policy blueprints can be linked to the survival criteria of technical feasibility, financial viability and value acceptability described by Kingdon (1984, 138ff.). These are set and used by experts themselves anticipating reactions e.g. from the public and policy-makers. Technical feasibility is closely related to the possible spatial structure of urban-regional open space concepts. Such concepts must, for instance, identify technically feasible ways of linking remaining open spaces to create a network beyond municipal borders. To this end, formal planning regulations have to be respected, including legal provisions on topics such as protected areas, renewable energies, water management, agriculture, etc. from state to municipal levels (Hartz 2018).

In terms of financial viability, the fact that urban-regional open space networks do not generate returns in monetary form means that their development is strongly dependent on public funding (Boulton & Dedekorkut-Howes 2024). Most of the concepts for these networks feature combined funding modalities that draw on resources from superior state programmes, financial contributions from member municipalities as well as funding and sponsoring by non-governmental organisations such as business associations or environmental protection groups (Gailing 2007). Such funding is not only limited in amount and time due to public budget restrictions, but can also be highly volatile, especially in the case of private donors (Macdonald et al. 2021b). It is therefore unsurprising that sufficient external funding is a crucial criterion for the adoption of an urban-regional open space concept.

Value acceptability refers to both, the anticipated value-based support from outside the policy community and the values or even ideologies of the experts themselves. Kingdon (1984, 140) mentions views on equity and efficiency as examples for such values. In the case of urban-regional open space strategies, the policy community relates to commonly accepted values such as improved quality of life, nature-friendly recreation and cultural landscape preservation (Gailing 2018, van der Stoep et al. 2017, Amati 2008). Even the specific financial burdens, organisational arrangements and constraints in land development that are part and parcel of

these strategies can be accepted by policy-makers if linked to other sanctioned values such as the solidarity of shared costs, voluntary collaboration, regional identity and competitiveness as well as sustainable land usage. Now we are in a position to formulate our fourth proposition:

P4 – Policy stream: Urban-regional open space strategies emerge as the result of long-term developments within policy communities that include policy transfer processes from general blueprints to specific regional arrangements. The drivers of the policy stream include technically-feasible spatial concepts, viable combined-funding modalities and value acceptability based on quality of life, landscape preservation and regional identity among others.

5.2.3 Political stream

According to Kingdon (1984, 160ff.), the dynamics of the political stream are driven by the turnover of policy-makers, the activities of interest groups and the public mood. These drivers can also be identified in the field of urban-regional open space policy. In terms of turnover, we see constant shifts and changes in leading political positions and coalitions, for instance following municipal or state elections or due to career promotions (Rautenstrauch 2015b, 12 f., Zimmermann & Feiertag 2021, 101, 247, Coleman et al. 2021). At the same time, some key actors at the intersection of politics and administration may hold influential positions for many years, thereby having a long-term impact on policies and political decisions linked to urban-regional open spaces (Gailing & Ibert 2016). This may allow them to take on the role of policy entrepreneurs, an MSF element that will be discussed in Part 5.2.4.

The literature on urban-regional open space policy typically identifies three types of actors associated with interest groups and their lobbying or advocacy activities as drivers of the political stream: business associations, environmental groups and farmers (e.g. Cruickshank 2018, Keil & Macdonald 2016, Amati & Taylor 2010, Freestone 2002). Business associations and other economic players are often described as actors in so-called 'growth coalitions' which promote urban sprawl rather than protecting and developing urban-regional open space networks (MacDonald et al. 2021b). For example, they can exert considerable pressure at municipal or higher levels using their powers as job creators and corporate taxpayers if open space concepts threaten their development perspectives (Monstadt & Meilinger 2020). However, according to other perspectives, these interest groups can also give substantial support to urban regional open space policies, as seen in the case of the Rhine-Main Regional Park (Dettmar 2014, Rautenstrauch 2015 a, b). Here, businesses and their associations benefit from the soft location factors provided by urban-regional open space networks (Lehmann & Rautenstrauch 2002, Krause 2014). These offer high recreational, leisure and tourism values, helping to create competitive advantages that will attract skilled workforce. In this sense, Selle's (1994) strategic approach to open space policy sees the incorporation of economic players as part of the solution (cf. Subsection 3.2).

Environmental and conservationist groups highlight the ecological value of open spaces, seeing their potential for the development of biotope networks (Mell 2010). In general, they support urban-regional open space strategies that include spatial planning concepts which help contain urban sprawl, protect the environment and raise ecological awareness (Macdonald et al. 2021a, b). In some cases, however, conservationist groups have been found to oppose specific urban-regional open space concepts or single projects, deeming them incompatible with

the idea of nature and environmental protection (Rautenstrauch 2015b). These groups often rely on volunteers, donations and project-bound funding, which may prevent them from forming strong structures and networks at regional level (Macdonald et al. 2021a, 156). Due to these inherent structural weaknesses, their potential influence on policy-makers is probably lower than that of business associations.

Farmers use, cultivate and/or own a substantial part of land that is interesting for planners of urban-regional open spaces (Lohrberg 2006). On the one hand, they may oppose strategies to create and develop open space networks, for instance if they view hiking and cycling pathways through their fields as obstacles interfering with their work and which threaten their livelihoods (Rautenstrauch 2015b, 20). Furthermore, as landowners, they may also perceive open space concepts as preventing them from exercising their property rights and from further developing their land (Pond 2009). On the other hand, farmers can also benefit from an urban-regional open strategy that conceptually involves their farms as points of interest for regional and sustainable agriculture or even through the establishment of farm shops (Dettmar 2014, Rautenstrauch 2015b, 76).

According to Kingdon, the final relevant driver of the political stream is the general mood within the population which may be also understood as “community expectation”, a factor identified by Boulton & Dedekorkut-Howes (2024, 10). The mood is monitored by political decision-makers, who may perceive it as for or against a particular policy or even observe “swings” (Kingdon 1984, 148). These perceptions will probably influence the position of policy-makers. In terms of urban-regional open space policy, one can expect the existence of such a regional (or at least local) mood or expectation that is both monitored by decision-makers and influenced by their decisions. For instance, in the prosperous German region of Stuttgart, the public mood has in recent years turned against any type of building project (Kiwitt & Hemberger 2022). In the UK, the local population generally supports the preservation of open spaces and the establishment of green belts (Sturzaker & Mell 2018, 55f, Bradely 2019). The key insight here can be summarised as follows:

P5 – Political stream: Turnover in leading political and administrative positions is a factor that influences the propensity and willingness to politically support the development of an urban-regional open space strategy. Business associations, conservationists and farmers are all organised interest groups that act as drivers, able to put pressure on policy-makers or to provide substantial support, albeit with varying degrees of power and influence. A diffuse regional mood is perceived by policy-makers, impacting their support and adoption of urban-regional open space strategies.

5.2.4 Policy entrepreneur and coupling

A policy is more likely to be successfully implemented when supported by the activities of a policy entrepreneur. Kingdon conceives this key actor as a knowledgeable, well-connected and highly motivated person or group of persons (Kingdon 1984, 189f.). One outstanding quality of policy entrepreneurs is their perception and use of windows of opportunity that allow them to couple the streams and to have the preferred policy adopted. In regard to regional planning, we only find a few explicit references to the concept of policy entrepreneurs (Gailing & Ibert 2016, Döringer 2020). However, similar ideas such as promoters, key actors or simply leadership

can be found in the field of open space and landscape planning (Fürst et al. 2005, Wende et al. 2009, van der Stoep 2017, Boulton & Dedekorkut-Howes 2024). Policy entrepreneurs are even specifically discussed in some studies (although the term here is “key actors”), such as Karl Ganser for the IBA Emscher Park (Pinch & Adams 2013) and Lorenz Rautenstrauch as the driving force behind the Rhine-Main Regional Park (MacDonald et al. 2021a, 151).

Policy entrepreneurs link a specific interpretation of a problem to the preferred solution, making a policy more appealing to policy-makers (Kingdon 1984). They achieve this by means of emotionalisation combined with knowledge-based arguments, also referred to as framing (Cairney 2018). As evidenced in the literature on MSF and as outlined by Selle (1994; Subsection 3.2), this strategic use of communication approaches is a recurring theme in the study of policy entrepreneurship in urban-regional open space policy (van der Stoep et al. 2017, Döringer 2020, Goode 2022), also related to as “positive story telling” (Siedentop et al. 2022, 669) or finding the right narrative or counter-narrative (Rigolon et al. 2022). The communication approach consists of framing a physical network of open spaces, e.g. as an attractive regional park (Gailing 2018) or green belt. This underlines the ideas of scenic landscapes and regional identity (Rautenstrauch 2015a). As we saw in the problem stream, landscapes are thus employed as symbols, although here they do not represent a deficient quality of life but rather help create a positive vision of space. Rautenstrauch even speaks of the “seductive” character of the park vision (2015b, 7, 28). As mentioned in Part 5.2.3, symbolic terms are often used to win the hearts and minds of influential actors and of the regional population, i.e. to sway the public mood (Faludi 1999, Bradley 2019). The antitypes of degraded landscapes and scenic landscapes fulfil this function, making an urban-regional open space concept termed as a regional park appear the most appropriate solution.

Another strategy frequently employed by policy entrepreneurs is the use or even the creation of various venues or arenas to bring the preferred solution forward (e.g. Huitema & Meijerink 2010, Cairney 2018, Hawkins & Krause 2023). In urban-regional open space policy this translates into formal and informal venues or arenas at different political administrative levels (Thomas & Littlewood 2010, 204). These can be meetings of regional planning associations for the adoption of regional land-use plans, joint thematic forums or even events taking place at (inter-)municipal level.

Until an open space strategy is adopted in the initial phase, policy entrepreneurship is focused on promoting policy change by coupling the three streams. In the implementation phase, there is a significant shift (as already discussed in Part 5.1.1) to policy stabilisation and the prevention of decoupling (Zahariadis & Exadaktylos 2016) in order to actually carry out and further develop the urban-regional open space concept. Another difference to the initial phase is that policy entrepreneurship in the implementation phase is often more institutionalised, as suggested by the report on the Rhine-Main Regional Park and other publications. Such entrepreneurship can be provided by an agency, unit or office for open space management (Rautenstrauch 2015a, Pond 2009, 250, Smith 2009). In this case, the agency has the inherent interest and motivation of a policy entrepreneur, namely to protect the regional open space network and push its development further. It is part of the activities of such institutionalised policy entrepreneurs to frame implemented projects as success stories, thereby gaining positive public and political feedback for a favourable evaluation (Petridou & Mintrom 2021). Nevertheless,

even with an institutionalised policy entrepreneur, it is possible that entrepreneurship can weaken, due, for instance, to changes in personnel. The previous lines can be summarised as follows:

P6 – Policy entrepreneurs and coupling: *Policy entrepreneurs couple the three streams by means of framing and communication strategies such as the construction of antitypes and the linking of emotions with knowledge-based arguments. They emphasise the aesthetic value of landscapes and evoke regional identity by framing open space networks as regional parks or green belts. Moreover, they can make use of different venues or arenas. In the initial phase, the coupling activities of policy entrepreneurs are geared towards promoting policy change. Then, during the implementation phase, entrepreneurial activities focus on stabilisation. Institutionalised entrepreneurship is likely to be ensured by an open space management unit or agency.*

5.2.5 Window(s) of opportunity

At the end of his report on the creation and development of the Rhine-Main Regional Park, Rautenstrauch (2015a, 114) concludes – without referring to Kingdon – that it owes its existence to a “time window” in which a certain favourable “constellation of conditions” occurred (transl. by authors). This can be easily interpreted as Kingdon’s policy window. With his focus on the agenda setting stage, Kingdon defined only one window of opportunity. In light of the stages of the policy cycle as outlined in Part 5.1.2, the concept of the window of opportunity must be adapted accordingly. Howlett (2019) posits the existence of a distinct window at the inception of each stage. While the opening of Kingdon’s policy window for agenda setting cannot be predicted (1984, 195ff.), Howlett postulates that further windows open automatically when the political process passes from one stage to another. Whether the transition from stage to stage really occurs or not depends on the interplay of the other four MSF elements.

As previously discussed, the concept of the policy cycle is applied to urban-regional open space policy-making and planning in a simplified way, i.e. we only distinguish an initial and an implementation phase. The same is true for the windows of opportunity: we posit an initial window (similar to Kingdon’s policy window) covering the phase until the adoption of a decision, i.e. an urban-regional open space concept. The implementation window then opens automatically once the decision on a concept has been adopted. This is applicable to both the sequence relating to the overall evolution of an open space network and the sequences, e.g. relating to major new implementation projects (Subsection 5.1). It should be noted that the implementation window also provides an opportunity to opposing policy entrepreneurs. Regarding the windows of opportunity, we can formulate the following proposition:

P7 – Windows of opportunity: *We have to distinguish two windows of opportunity related, firstly, to the overall, long-term development sequence and, secondly, to the short-term sequences within the implementation phase. While it cannot be predicted if or when an initial window for the potential adoption of an urban-regional open space policy will open, a later window of opportunity (or ‘implementation window’) will open automatically at the beginning of the implementation phase after the decision has been adopted.*

5.2.6 Decoupling risks in the implementation phase

The longer the period of implementation, the higher the probability that streams which were coupled in the initial phase start to decouple, leading to failure and termination of the policy (Zahariadis & Exadaktylos 2016, 78). Against this backdrop, we turn now to the issue of implementation risks, which can arise in all three streams, as well as on entrepreneurial activities to counter such risks. Regarding the risks in the problem stream, it is possible that other (economic) problems such as a lack of housing or the expansion of renewable energy infrastructures may be perceived as more urgent. Another risk is that, due to the enhancement of landscapes through the implemented projects, one key factor of the original problem loses weight, namely the personal experience of degraded landscapes. In this case, policy entrepreneurship may make use of what we can call “problem updating”, which involves searching, defining and framing new problems such as climate change mitigation and adaptation (Amati & Taylor 2010, Schwarze-Rodrian 2016, Goode 2022) that can be coupled to the open space strategy.

In the case of risks stemming from the policy stream, the above-mentioned survival criteria of technical feasibility, financial viability or value acceptability play a crucial role. Technical feasibility might be affected by new planning regulations or laws in the building code (Monstadt & Meilinger 2020) or in environmental law such as compensatory restoration (Mac Donald et al. 2021a) or through territorial reforms entailing a change of competencies (Rautenstrauch 2015a, Bradely 2019). The financial viability of urban-regional open space concepts can be affected by changes in funding at state, national or EU level (Rautenstrauch 2015a), for instance the European Regional Development Fund (Zepp 2018). Dwindling financial support may make the urban-regional open space strategy less attractive, accompanied by a decline in acceptance (Pinch & Adams 2013). Finally, the value acceptability of an adopted policy may change when a stronger focus is placed on economic competitiveness between municipalities, thereby reducing their willingness to adhere to values such as collaboration or shared financial contributions. Consequently, the original solutions may seem less suitable for solving the perceived problems. Here policy entrepreneurship can suggest alternative convincing solutions for all design dimensions by adapting the policy to the new technical, financial and value-related requirements. One example is to take up the green infrastructure concept (Mell 2011, Schwarze-Rodrian 2016, Zimmermann & Lee 2021, Mengueti & Oliveira 2021), which allows the integration of new technical planning categories such as flood protection. It can also be used to identify new funding opportunities at state, national and EU level (Slätmo et al. 2019) as well as to foster intermunicipal collaboration (Roggema 2020).

With regard to the political stream, changes in government coalitions or key political-administrative positions at state, regional or even local level can potentially undermine support for urban-regional open space strategies. To prevent this risk, entrepreneurial activities may aim at maintaining the support of these (new) influential actors and beneficiaries of the open space policy. Policy entrepreneurs can achieve this by framing the open space strategy as a non-partisan issue. In this sense, it is important that they present implemented projects as a success, emphasising their popularity with the general public. Together with established networks at all levels, these elements can be decisive in ensuring long-lasting political support for the further development and consolidation of the policy (Sturzaker & Mell 2018, Bradely 2019). This leads to our final proposition:

P8 – Decoupling risks in the implementation phase: *During implementation, risks arising in any of the three streams can cause the streams to decouple, resulting in the failure and termination of the urban-regional open space strategy. Accordingly, entrepreneurial activities must focus on stream-specific approaches to counter these risks.*

6. Discussion of the approach

Our discussion begins by describing the positive features of the developed MSF-based theoretical approach (Subsection 6.1). Then two interrelated key questions are explored: To which degree is policy-making and planning marked by messiness and randomness? And: To which degree can policy entrepreneurs exert influence (6.2). Subsection 6.3 deals with the limitations of the developed approach regarding possible alternatives to the MSF and its applicability to different countries. Finally, we outline some implications for research and practice (Subsection 6.4).

6.1 Strengths of the developed MSF-based approach

The present conceptual development was triggered, on the one hand, by the simple fact that policy process theories have seldom been employed to explain urban-regional open space policy-making and planning, and on the other hand, by the rather anecdotal evidence that a practitioner's report on the evolution of the Rhine-Main Regional Park corresponds very well with the MSF. In our research we synthesised two strands of literature and thus were able to confirm that the MSF, which has been applied to many other policy fields, can also be reasonably employed for the analysis of urban-regional open space policy-making and planning. Interpreting and adapting the multiple streams concept, we developed an MSF-based theoretical approach tailored to the characteristics of this field (see Fig. 1). In our view, the set of eight qualitative propositions represents plausible expectations of how urban-regional open space policy-making and planning work from a policy process perspective. It seems that a sufficient initial degree of complexity and consistency has been reached.

It is essential that the developed approach is able to explicitly take into account the often-found ambiguity and messiness of policy-making. This it mainly does through the concept of independent streams and policy windows, which is the hallmark of the MSF. However, it also systematically integrates many factors discussed in the wider literature on open space policy-making and planning, particularly the key role of individuals as well as the framing of problems and policies. Moreover, the approach identifies an initial and an implementation phase, also introducing a new view on policy and planning implementation based on the idea that coupled streams may later decouple. Given the recent developments of the MSF and the availability of other theories, there is some potential to deepen and extend the presented theoretical approach. Finally, as it also positions experts and planners clearly within policy-making, it can be a useful complement to popular planning theories as presented, for example, by Rydin (2021). In particular, the notion that planners, as experts in the policy stream, can in principle also take on the role of policy entrepreneurs, fits well with ongoing discussions in planning theory (e.g. Moroni 2020).

6.2 Degree of messiness and entrepreneurial influence

Some scholars have criticised the original MSF for being overly vague (e.g. Rawat & Morris 2016, Herweg et al. 2018). The current authors also encountered significant vagueness, for instance regarding the definition of the streams as well as the interrelations between streams and actors. We hope that our interpretation and adjustments help to reduce this vagueness, at least with regard to urban-regional open space policy-making and planning. However, there remains the key question of the degree of expected messiness, randomness or unpredictability of significant policy change, which is linked to the question of controllability of processes and the role of entrepreneurial influence. This issue, only briefly touched upon in Subsection 4.1, is of utmost importance for deriving policy advice from the theoretical approach.

As a key feature of his framework on agenda setting, Kingdon conceptualises a structure consisting of the three streams, which are “largely independent of one another” and which develop according to their “own dynamics and rules.” (1984, 20). In a strict understanding, this implies that the streams mainly converge in a random fashion. Moreover, it means that policy entrepreneurs are scarcely able to influence the streams in order to couple them at some desirable point in time, but have to wait for the three streams to become favourable and for an event signalling a window of opportunity. Policy entrepreneurs are conceptualised as acting to convince receptive policy-makers who advocate a certain policy from the policy stream in order to solve a certain problem from the problem stream (Kingdon 1984, 188ff.). There is no mention of policy entrepreneurs influencing the streams.

However, this view is challenged (Herweg et al. 2018, 39). Indeed, one may even refer to Kingdon himself, who, at the end of his book, feels the need to make sure there are no misunderstandings. This could be interpreted as a relativisation of his theory. In particular, he emphasises that the approach is probabilistic and not deterministic (1984, 218), i.e. it fundamentally deals with likelihood and odds. More significantly, he seems to de-emphasise the aspect of randomness in policy-making, only stating that “[t]here remains some degree of unpredictability.” (1984, 216). Furthermore, he points out that “it would be a grave mistake to conclude that the processes explored (...) are essentially random.” (1984, 216). He explains this by referring to processes within each stream which limit randomness. In the political stream, for instance, some changes in the mood are less likely than others; Kingdon highlights the unlikelihood of the national mood in the USA turning to socialism. Moreover, he argues that interest groups may have different resources on hand to influence policy-makers. Despite these two relativising arguments, there is no doubt that Kingdon basically assumes a certain level of unpredictability and uncontrollability.

A completely contrasting view is held by Cairney (2018, 200, 209), for whom it is possible for an entrepreneur to be dominant in all streams, “like Poseidon”. Cairney particularly refers to lower politico-administrative levels, where single actors can generally exert greater influence on other relevant actors and discussions. This seems plausible, especially when a strong political leader, e.g. the mayor of a town, takes on the role of policy entrepreneur and makes a certain policy their personal top priority. However, this precondition hardly holds true for our primary interest, namely regional governance settings. In such multi-actor settings, the possibility of exerting influence is dispersed.

To really understand the possibility of influencing the streams, we need to return to their drivers. Of course, some of these are entirely resistant to outside influence, such as catastrophes, while others can be influenced to a certain degree, depending on the position of a policy entrepreneur in the political system. However, it is generally difficult to imagine a case in which a policy entrepreneur is able to significantly influence the streams so as to increase the likelihood of policy adoption. In our view (and in line with Kingdon), therefore, the policy entrepreneur is best conceptualised as directing their persuasive efforts towards policy-makers. Regarding the political stream, for instance, a prominent driver is the public mood. Clearly, it is a key aim of regional open space strategies to gain the hearts and minds of the public in favour of open space networks. Yet it would be misplaced to think that a policy entrepreneur can influence this driver in order to change policy decisions. Rather, he or she can advocate a *corresponding* policy which should be adopted and implemented. In this sense Fig. 1 could be complemented with a feedback loop running from the policy on the right-hand side back to the respective stream on the left-hand side. While Kingdon showed that (process) structures in the form of the streams and individual actions of a policy entrepreneur together lead to a policy decision (cf. Ritter & Lancaster 2018, 232), an added feedback loop shows how policies can aim to change these structures – albeit with uncertain prospects of success.

As the discussion so far has implicitly referred to Kingdon's agenda setting stage, we also need to ask whether the stated arguments on stream independence and possible influence on streams also hold true for stages beyond agenda setting, i.e. the policy formation and decision-making stages (initial phase) and the implementation phase. There is much to suggest that streams maintain a certain dynamic of their own, and that decoupling can, in principle, happen at any time, through any of the stages or phases. This holds true even in the policy formation stage, when planning and politics are particularly closely aligned. It could be argued that stream independence is undermined because experts who prepare policies, such as landscape and spatial planners, are often – due to employment or service contracts – directly dependent on policy-makers. Even then, general blueprints develop independently and experts may retain a certain influence and room for manoeuvre. Moreover, the opinions of policy-makers may shift due to changing problem perceptions, dissatisfaction with the formulated policy and changes in personnel.

All in all, there seem to be varying degrees of randomness or unpredictability as well as controllability and individual influence. Taking into account Kingdon's relativisations and partly following Herweg et al. (2018, 39f.), it seems reasonable to view the MSF as an analytical approach which *includes the possibility* of a range of degrees of randomness and a range of degrees of influence by individuals. However, this necessarily provokes the question: Which circumstances lead to which degrees of randomness and which degree of influence by individuals? Obviously, the policy field, the significance of the policy, the politico-administrative level and the time horizon under consideration play important roles. Ultimately, empirical research is needed to provide an answer. Kingdon offers the appropriate theoretical basis for such investigations (Herweg et al. 2018, 39, Ritter & Lancaster 2018, 235).

6.3 Alternatives to MSF and limited international applicability

Reflecting further on the significance and limitations of the suggested MSF-based approach, two aspects need to be highlighted. First, it is clear that here we are not offering an all-embracing theory of urban-regional open space policy. On the one hand, it would be possible to derive more refinements to the approach from the literature on open space policy and planning and related fields; and on the other, there exists a range of other possible frameworks and general theories of policy-making and planning which could be used. These latter draw in part on other ontological and epistemological perspectives and focus on different aspects.

For instance, the MSF realistically acknowledges that actors can have various degrees of influence or power. However, it addresses conflicts only indirectly, presupposing that struggles within the streams and between policy entrepreneurs were decided in favour of the policy change that it explains. In contrast, one could choose an approach that explicitly focuses on power and is more critical of society, for instance in a politico-ecological or post-structuralist approach. As the MSF does not focus on institutions, institutional theories could alternatively be deployed (Smith 2009, Macdonald et al. 2021b). There are in fact several policy process frameworks to choose from (Orach & Schlüter 2016, Weible 2023). One example is the Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF), which focuses on what in the MSF is called the political stream. Accordingly, Howlett et al. (2017) suggest incorporating this into the MSF. As our example shows, the MSF is open to further extensions or combinations with other approaches. Moreover, governance approaches highlighting the interaction of a multitude of actors at several politico-administrative levels (Görg 2007, Leibenath & Lintz 2017) could help complement the picture from the perspective of policy science. Moving beyond this discipline, for instance to sociology, long-term societal changes which influence the basic mood of the population may be of interest, such as in the development of general human-nature relationships. Importantly, this shows the relevance of considering how wider societal framework conditions change when conducting long-term investigations based on the MSF.

Secondly, it is also clear that the theoretical approach to the field of urban-regional open space policy is not expected to be applicable to all types of political and planning systems. In the main, it refers to pluralistic democratic countries with complex multi-level governance and a minimum of sectoral policy and planning structures designed to correct failures in the market system, which largely underpins the economy. The application of the MSF to undemocratic political systems may be possible but will require significant modifications (Herweg et al. 2018, 45).

6.4 Implications for research and practice

Regarding the implications for further research, we suggest that scholars could empirically examine the extent to which the MSF-based approach derived from the literature can indeed explain significant policy decisions with regard to urban-regional open space policy-making and planning. On the basis of the formulated propositions, it would be useful to determine whether the elements or factors of the developed approach can be identified and their expected interactions confirmed. The empirical investigation could start using causal-process tracing (Blatter & Haverland 2014), first taking successful examples followed by examples

where an initiative failed or initial success could not be sustained. Then definitions and relationships between factors could be refined and the scope of reasonable application explored.

There exist additional important aspects which have not been included in the theoretical approach discussed here, for instance with regard to the above-mentioned further MSF developments which were not considered in this stage of theory building. Furthermore, research could usefully focus on particularly interesting elements of the MSF or widen the view to other, neighbouring policy fields such as spatial planning or spatial sustainability transformation policy. It would be particularly interesting to learn more about the circumstances which influence randomness and the scope of possible entrepreneurial agency. Regarding the general applicability of the MSF, we must consider two related questions. In developing his framework, Kingdon referred to Victor Hugo's famous dictum about "an idea whose time has come" (Kingdon 1984, 1). Here we can ask: When is a policy idea of sufficient importance to be reasonably analysed using the MSF? According to Ritter and Lancaster (2018, 235), the MSF is the right approach "for analysing a process which is complex, ambiguous and somewhat serendipitous." The second related question is thus: What level of complexity, ambiguity and serendipity is sufficient to justify the use of the MSF?

As systematic empirical research is still pending, the implications for practical policy-making and planning in favour of urban-regional open spaces can only be derived from theoretical considerations (see also Lintz 2024). These offer somewhat ambiguous advice for relevant actors. On the one hand, the MSF highlights the possibility of randomness or chance in political success. In the case of a relatively high degree of randomness, this suggests that politicians, experts and activists need to practice the discipline of patience and humbleness. On the other hand, policy entrepreneurs, and those who want to act as such, can, if they see some chance of success, always try to push their policy proposals and defend their adopted policies – in the end, the MSF is only probabilistic (Kingdon 1984, 218). In any case, the MSF may help assess this chance and inform action by drawing on the guidance by Cairney (2018) to focus on the most promising activities related to the five elements of the theoretical approach. In this sense, perseverance and tenacity may pay off.

7. Conclusion

By synthesising two relevant strands of literature, we have developed a theoretical approach that explains the adoption and implementation of urban-regional open space policies (such as regional park and green belt strategies) focusing on policy-making and planning processes. For this, Kingdon's (1984) well-established Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) is specifically interpreted and adapted. The approach comprises the five elements of the MSF and extends it over several phases of the policy cycle. We believe that our set of eight propositions offers plausible expectations of how urban-regional open space policy-making and planning work in many countries from a policy process perspective while highlighting the frequent ambiguity and messiness of policy-making. The approach, which integrates many relevant factors and is open to further extensions, provides a complementary understanding of this policy field and may also benefit the comprehension of related policy fields such as common spatial planning as well as sustainability transformation policy. For scholars of political science, the new application of the MSF may provide insights for a more general development of the framework. We

think that our MSF-based approach derived from the literature is sufficiently mature to be further operationalised and subject to systematic qualitative empirical testing in order to create a more advanced theory. Despite some significant constraints, the approach can already improve the basis for strategy development to the benefit of all actors who wish to achieve and defend sustainable patterns of land use.

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